

< **WAD**cher/>

Public final report

Deliverable D1.5 :: Public

Keywords: WADcher, web accessibility, Web Accessibility Directive, WAD, European Union, European Commission, Horizon 2020, public sector, evaluation of websites

Web Accessibility
Directive Decision
Support Environment

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	6
2	The Consortium	7
2.1	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V., Fraunhofer FIT	7
2.2	The National Microelectronics Applications Centre LTD.....	8
2.3	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Laboratory on Human Interfaces in Information Systems.....	8
2.4	Hilfsgemeinschaft der Blinden und Sehschwachen Österreichs	9
2.5	Agenzia per l'Italia Digitale.....	9
2.6	DEXTERA Consulting Ltd.....	10
2.7	Hellenic Ministry for Health	10
2.8	Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas	11
3	Background information: the EU Web Accessibility Directive (WAD).....	12
3.1	Overview	12
3.2	European Accessibility Act	13
4	Project outcomes.....	15
4.1	Supported stakeholders	16
4.2	WADcher Services	16
4.2.1	WADcher APIs.....	21
4.3	Automatic Evaluation Tools	22
4.3.1	imergo® Web Compliance Suite	22
4.3.2	MAUVE.....	23
4.3.3	WaaT.....	23
4.3.4	Madis	23
5	WADcher Pilot Reference Sites.....	25
6	Future steps.....	26
7	Contact and acknowledgements	27

List of Figures

Figure 1 Infographic: Digital Inclusion in the EU..... 13

Figure 2 Graphical representation of the scope of the project. 16

Figure 3. WADcher Observatory displaying an overview of the audit results..... 18

Figure 4. WADcher DSE providing assertions to experts and developers..... 19

Figure 5. WADcher Monitor Service providing to the Monitoring Body a graphical comparison of accessibility audits. 19

Figure 6. WADcher Monitor Service providing to the Monitoring Body a territorial overview. 20

Figure 7 WADcher APIs Homepage..... 22

List of Tables

Table 1 WADcher benefits for each user group..... 21

Contractual Date of Delivery to the EC:	2021-06-30		
Actual Date of Delivery to the EC:	2021-10-15 (reviewed)		
Editors:	Carlos A Velasco, Yehya Mohamad (Fraunhofer)		
Contributors:	Carlos A Velasco, Yehya Mohamad (Fraunhofer), John O'Flaherty (MAC), Aggeliki Spyrou, Dimitrios Tzovaras (CERTH/ITI), Fabiò Paterno (CNR)		
DOCUMENT HISTORY			
Version	Version date	Responsible	Description
0.1	2021-06-21	Fraunhofer	First Table of Contents
0.5	2021-06-30	Fraunhofer	Stable Draft
0.9	2021-07-19	MAC, CERTH	Comments and updates
1.0	2021-07-28	Fraunhofer	Final version
2.0	2021-10-15	Fraunhofer	Updated version

WADcher¹ (Web Accessibility Directive Decision Support Environment) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 780206.

The information and views set out in this publication are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Communities. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5579307

Copyright © 2021 WADcher Consortium. Permission is granted to copy, distribute and/or modify this document text and its contained artworks under the Creative Commons Attribution License 3.0 as described at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0>.

¹ <https://wadcher.eu/>

1 Executive Summary

This document contains a summary of the results and scope of the WADcher project addressed to the general public. The project addresses the challenges people with various degrees of disabilities face when accessing mainstream online products and services, thus being excluded from benefiting from Web content and services on an equal basis as people without disabilities. Marginalising people with disabilities on this level is a critical and problematic issue, especially in today's "Information Society", where access to information should be equally available to all. While these challenges have been identified (also by the EC with the published Web Accessibility Directive (WAD), which entered into force on 22/12/2016), they have not yet been addressed efficiently. In this context and building on ongoing tools, WADcher researched, developed and demonstrated a set of innovative frameworks: an Observatory, a Decision Support Environment (DSE) and a Monitor Service, for large scale hybrid web accessibility assessment services and WAD compliance by implementing the monitoring, reporting and enforcement procedures of the WAD in all European public sector websites, while minimising costs and development-time along with increased scalability, accessibility and usability for all stakeholders, to enable "Web Access by Default".

2 The Consortium

The WADcher Consortium consists of 8 organisations from 6 different countries (Germany, Austria, Greece, Italy, Ireland and Cyprus) representing a wide representation of Europe in terms of population, culture and economic power. The consortium is composed of three leading research organisations, two SMEs, two public authorities and one end user organisation. All partners have been involved in international R&D projects before and many of them have worked together in several of such projects and brought their collective knowledge into the WADcher project.

The consortium members are briefly described in the following sections.

2.1 Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V., Fraunhofer FIT

The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.² is a link between science and industry, between research and the application of its results. It was founded in Munich in 1949 as a non-profit registered association. The organisation takes its name from Joseph von Fraunhofer (1787–1826), the successful Munich researcher, inventor and entrepreneur. The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft is an autonomous organization with a decentralised organisational structure, which currently maintains 66 institutes and research units in locations throughout Germany and other countries. The majority of its nearly 24,000 employees are qualified scientists and engineers. Its current annual research budget totals €2 billion, from which €1.7 billion is generated through contract research with industry and from publicly financed research projects, being the leading organisation of institutes of applied research and development in Europe.

The Fraunhofer-Institut für Angewandte Informationstechnik FIT³ (Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology FIT) helps to shape the future with novel, user-oriented products. Fraunhofer FIT has a staff of about 120 researchers from Computer Science, Engineering, Social Sciences, Psychology, Business Administration and Economics. They work in interdisciplinary teams and combine insights from computer science and engineering with input from other fields. Our specific strength is a comprehensive user-centred system design process, from test and validation of concepts to the handover of sustainable and performant systems.

A product relevant to the project is the imergo[®] Web Compliance Suite,⁴ developed by Fraunhofer FIT. This suite is licensed worldwide to different Enterprise Content Management System (ECMS) manufacturers. imergo[®] encompasses a suite of tools that supports its customers when implementing Quality Assurance methods and processes targeted to Web Compliance. This suite is mainly used by its customers to test accessibility and standards compliance. imergo[®] is a product aimed to mobile and large websites offering an open REST API to interact with other applications.

² <https://fraunhofer.de/>

³ <https://fit.fraunhofer.de/>

⁴ <https://imergo.com/>

2.2 The National Microelectronics Applications Centre LTD

The National Microelectronics Applications Centre (MAC⁵) was established in 1981, by the Irish Government, to provide consultancy and complete innovative development and exploitation of electronic, software and e-business/e-government citizen participation technological solutions. MAC is an innovative SME with a 40 year track record of delivering to tight schedules with industry, SMEs and public agencies to assess and assist entrepreneurial and innovative technical solutions. To date, MAC has delivered 230 leading edge product developments, 35 Web/online services, 175 process applications, 490 consultancy projects, 33 pan-European technology development consortia and 3,000 new idea evaluations. These have enabled the growth of several multi-million Euro companies. We have completed numerous evaluations, studies and outsourced R&D projects for European companies where we act as the innovator and designer of their future services and product set.

The parallel activity of the company in working with entrepreneurs, SMEs, and administrations to deliver operational solutions, grounds this work in the real commercial world ensuring that MAC's staff is a focused team of highly flexible, motivated, responsive, pragmatic and experienced technical, research and project management experts, who can both manage distributed outsourced development teams and its own in-house technical staff.

2.3 Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Laboratory on Human Interfaces in Information Systems

The Information Science and Technologies Institute (CNR-ISTI⁶) aims at increasing knowledge, developing and testing new ideas in ICT, and widening the application areas. The Institute is structured into a number of laboratories. The laboratory involved in this project is the Laboratory on Human Interfaces in Information Systems.⁷ The main goal of this laboratory is to investigate new solutions in basic and applied research in the field of human-computer interaction, user interface software and interactive information systems, in particular to obtain methods and tools to support user interface designers and developers to obtain usable systems accessible from different contexts of use.

One of the main areas of interest is Tools for Accessibility and Usability Evaluation. CNR supports various techniques ranging from intelligent analysis of logs of user interactions detected on the users' devices to code inspection in order to check whether consistency with relevant guidelines. The tool developed for accessibility validation is MAUVE (MultiguideLine Accessibility and Usability Validation Environment). It supports validation separated from guidelines' definition, guidelines formalized through an XML language, capable of expressing all the past, present and (virtually) future accessibility guidelines, browser's plugin for the validation of dynamically created/modified Web pages, possibility of analyzing the versions of a web-site specific for certain types of device (e.g. mobile versions, desktop version, etc.), potentially expandable as a system for continuous monitoring of accessibility of web sites' sets.

⁵ <https://www.mac.ie/>

⁶ <https://www.isti.cnr.it/en/>

⁷ <https://hiis.isti.cnr.it/lab/home>

2.4 Hilfgemeinschaft der Blinden und Sehschwachen Österreichs

The Hilfgemeinschaft der Blinden und Sehschwachen Österreichs (Austrian Association in Support of the Blind and Visually Impaired⁸) exists since 1935 as a secular, non-profit association without affiliations to a political party or group. The goal is to improve the living conditions of visually impaired and blind people. At present, we provide support and guidance for about 4,000 members from all over Austria. Almost all Hilfgemeinschaft activities are funded from private donations. Serious and transparent donations management is an overriding concern in our work. The Hilfgemeinschaft has held the Donations Management Quality Seal since 2001. Our donors can be sure that we manage their donations precisely as they intended.

Membership is free for visually impaired and blind people, and enables them to access many services free of charge. Some of the key activities of the HG are:

- library for the blind (conversion to accessible formats)
- free Braille courses as well as computer courses (ECDL for blind and visually impaired)
- low-cost rental of CCTV (closed-circuit television)
- low-vision aids counselling
- in-depth conversations with psychological supervision, therapeutic art groups
- wide range of leisure activities (cultural, social and sports)
- lectures, excursions with sighted tutors, language courses etc.
- lobbying regarding the position of persons with disabilities on a national and international level, participation in conferences (ICCHP; AAATE, m-enable, ...)
- cooperation with other national and international organisations in projects, laws, standards and regulations (AIT, ASI, AAL-Projects, etc.)
- running of a pension house in Lower Austria (100 beds) for elderly persons with visual impairment

2.5 Agenzia per l'Italia Digitale

The National Agency for Digital Italy (AgID⁹) is the Government agency responsible for the implementation of the Italian Digital Agenda. The Agency is the Italian representative at EU level, in the subjects of its competence. Furthermore, AGID promotes the definition and development of large strategic projects of research and innovation related to the implementation of the Italian Digital Agenda and in conformity to the European program Horizon 2020.

The Agency supports public administrations in their effective adoption and use of ICT, improving quality of services and reducing costs, with broad competences in e-Government, information society and technology innovation, including such areas as new generation networks, security, open standards, e-health, digital literacy, open data, online education, digital inclusion, and smart communities.

⁸ <https://www.hilfgemeinschaft.at/>

⁹ <https://www.agid.gov.it/>

It identifies and promotes the main principles and rules on interoperability, usability, accessibility, etc. to be carried out by PAs in order to implement and sustain in the long term concrete and shared objectives and actions.

2.6 DEXTERA Consulting Ltd

DEXTERA Consulting Ltd¹⁰ is a consulting and software development SME, specialized in the design and engineering of business intelligence and other decision support systems. DEXTERA was founded in 2006 and since then it has successfully delivered products and solutions to businesses and authorities in southeast Europe, mainly in the field of healthcare.

The business strategy of DEXTERA includes research and development of advanced technologies, to create a bucket of solutions and products that would be useful to every business or authority, namely: Mobile applications, Mobile first web portals and services, Dashboards and visual analytics, Interactive Maps, Decision Support Knowledge Bases, Data warehouses, all aiming to support decision makers receive informed decisions in the area of their matter expertise.

DEXTERA disposes expertise in web and mobile development, but mainly in the field of visual analytics and business intelligence. The frameworks DEXTERA is using for development include both open source and Microsoft .NET technologies. In the business intelligence context the preferred tools include Microsoft B.I. stack, SAS and Tableau.

Since many of the company's clients are public authorities, the engineering team of DEXTERA is well trained and following strict processes on the compliance of their products with web accessibility regulations and best practices. The team is continuously experimenting with new web and mobile platforms, development libraries, content authoring and multi-channel presentation tools to assist decision makers take informed decisions within the context of their matter expertise, etc.

2.7 Hellenic Ministry for Health

The mission of the **Hellenic Ministry for Health** (MoH¹¹) is the provision of quality healthcare services to the general population in Greece. Under the supervision of the ministry, operates the Primary Healthcare Network (PEDY) with more than 1,200 primary healthcare centers around the country and 126 public hospitals with over 25,000 beds. MoH has an extended field of action, including management of emergency medical services, Public Health, humanitarian approach to victims of natural or manmade disasters, telemedicine provision, health coverage of major events and European cooperation.

The National Health Coordination and Command Center (EKEPY), which was involved in the project, is an executive agency of MoH and was founded in 2004, initially in order to cover the needs of the Olympic Games of Athens 2004. EKEPY is the main operational tool for the Minister of Health. The role of EKEPY is the supervision and coordination of all healthcare services (public and private), especially in crisis situations, as well as the recreation of National Health Policies (Policy maker).

¹⁰ <https://www.dexteraconsulting.com/>

¹¹ <https://www.moh.gov.gr/>

MoH invests continuously in IT systems to manage and monitor the operations and cost centers of the public healthcare system, but also to provide quality services to the citizens. These include several enterprise level web applications and web portals providing crucial information to citizens who would like to receive healthcare services, but also to practitioners and administrative personnel.

The departments of the ministry employ highly experienced personnel who are operating the aforementioned applications, disposing both technical and customer service skills. These people will be an asset for the WADcher project since they will be in position to handle to engagement with the citizens interacting with the web portals.

2.8 Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas

The **Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas** (CERTH¹²) is the only research centre in Northern Greece and one of the largest in the country and it was founded in 2000. It is a legal entity governed by private law with non-profit status, supervised by the General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) of the Greek Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs. CERTH has important scientific and technological achievements in many areas including: Energy, Environment, Industry, Mechatronics, Information & Communication, Transportation & Sustainable Mobility, Health, Agro-biotechnology, Smart farming, Safety & Security, as well as several cross-disciplinary scientific areas.

In 2008, CERTH was among the first Greek research organisations to undersign and accept the principles of the Charter and Code for researchers while at the same time CERTH's representatives were members of the Greek delegation at the Steering Group for Human Resources and Mobility (SG HRM). Its latest achievement in the field of human resources is the "HR EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH" logo awarded by the EC in April 2012 as a proof that CERTH is committed to offer the best possible working conditions, regardless the socioeconomic environment, and at the same time works towards the realisation of the European Research Area (Innovation Union, Commitment #4). In the WADcher project, the Information Technologies Institute (ITI) Institute will participate.

The Information Technologies Institute (ITI¹³) was founded in 1998 as a non-profit organisation under the auspices of the General Secretariat for Research and Technology of the Greek Ministry of Development, with its head office located in Thessaloniki, Greece. Since 10/03/2000 it is a founding member of the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) also supervised by the General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT).

CERTH/ITI has participated in more than 175 research projects funded by the European Commission (FP5-FP6-FP7 & H2020) and more than 100 research projects funded by Greek National Research Programmes and Consulting Subcontracts with the Private Sector (Industry). The last three years, the Information Technologies Institute has attracted an income of more than 25.5 M€ from National and European competitive R&D projects. For the last 10 years, the publication record of ITI includes more than 270 scientific publications in international journals, more than 600 publications in conferences and 100 books and book chapters. These works have been cited in more than 6.500 times.

¹² <https://www.certh.gr/>

¹³ <https://www.iti.gr/iti/index.html>

3 Background information: the EU Web Accessibility Directive (WAD)

3.1 Overview

Web technologies and mobile apps have become an essential means to delivering and accessing information and services. With 1 in 4 people in the EU aged 16 or over suffering from a long-term disability¹⁴ and an ageing population, web accessibility has become crucial. Web accessibility means that everyone, including persons with disabilities, will be able to better perceive, understand, navigate, and interact with the Internet. Web accessibility thus enables the participation of millions of Europeans that may otherwise be at risk of exclusion from the digital society.

The EU has, and is, doing much to raise awareness of digital inclusion and accessibility among the design, development, usability, and related communities who build, shape, fund and influence technology and its use, to ensure that European Digital Economy and Society legislation is there for everyone, regardless of their ability (see Figure 1).

A major initiative to address this is the EU Directive on the “Accessibility of the Websites and Mobile Applications of Public Sector Bodies¹⁵” that came into force on 26/10/2016, also known as the Web Accessibility Directive (WAD), which establishes accessibility requirements for the websites and mobile applications of public sector bodies.

The WAD defines accessibility as “*principles and techniques to be observed when designing, constructing, maintaining, and updating websites and mobile applications in order to make them more accessible to users, in particular persons with disabilities*”. The content of websites and mobile applications includes textual as well as non-textual information, downloadable documents and forms, and two-way interaction such as the processing of digital forms and the completion of authentication, identification, and payment processes.

The WAD’s accessibility requirements describe what must be achieved for the user to be able to perceive, operate, interpret, and understand a website, a mobile application and related content. But it does not specify what technology should be selected for each website, online information, or mobile application. WAD defines mobile applications as “*application software designed and developed, by or on behalf of public sector bodies, for use by the general public on mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets. It does not include the software that controls those devices (mobile operating systems) or hardware*”.

The WAD aims to ensure that the websites and mobile applications of public sector bodies are made more accessible based on common accessibility requirements. It defines the four principles of accessibility as (based upon the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines, WCAG, 2.1, W3C Recommendation 05 June 2018¹⁶):

- **perceivability**, meaning that information and user interface components must be presentable to users in ways they can perceive;

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/EDN-20181203-1>

¹⁵ <https://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/2102/oj>

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/>

- **operability**, meaning that user interface components and navigation must be operable;
- **understandability**, meaning that information and the operation of the user interface must be understandable; and
- **robustness**, meaning that content must be robust enough to be interpreted reliably by a wide variety of user agents, including assistive technologies.

Figure 1 Infographic: Digital Inclusion in the EU.¹⁷

3.2 European Accessibility Act

While the WAD specifically addresses the accessibility of websites and mobile applications of public sector bodies, and the **Harmonised European Standard Accessibility requirements for ICT products and services** (EN 301 549 V2.1.2, 2018-08¹⁸) addresses those and some additional ICT services, the **European Accessibility Act** (EAA¹⁹) addresses the much broader accessibility of all ICT services. The EAA aims to improve the functioning of the EU internal market for accessible products and services by removing barriers created by divergent legislation. This facilitates the work of companies and brings benefits for persons with disabilities and elderly people in the EU.

¹⁷ Full original is at https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=59213

¹⁸ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_en/301500_301599/301549/02.01.02_60/en_301549v020102p.pdf

¹⁹ Directive (EU) 2019/882 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on the accessibility requirements for products and services (Text with EEA relevance).

ELI: <https://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/882/oj>

After consulting with stakeholders and experts on accessibility and considering the obligations deriving from the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities²⁰ the Commission identified the following products and services should be addressed by the EAA, as having the highest risk of being concerned with diverging accessibility requirements across the EU countries:²¹

- computers and operating systems
- ATMs, ticketing and check-in machines
- smartphones
- TV equipment related to digital television services
- telephony services and related equipment
- audio-visual media services such as television broadcast and related consumer equipment
- services related to air, bus, rail and waterborne passenger transport
- banking services
- e-books
- e-commerce

While there is some overlap with the WAD, the EAA is much broader in scope, so that **businesses benefit from:**

- common rules on accessibility in the EU, leading to costs reduction
- easier cross-border trading
- more market opportunities for their accessible products and services

While persons with disabilities and elderly people benefit from:

- more accessible products and services in the market
- accessible products and services at more competitive prices
- fewer barriers when accessing education and the open labour market
- more jobs available where accessibility expertise is needed

The EU co-legislators adopted the EAA directive in April 2019. It is important to ensure, as the accessibility requirements are the same as under the WAD, that consistency is kept when assessing technical compliance with the accessibility requirements. However, enforcement is very different in both directives, with the EAA stressing the European CEN standard 17161 on accessibility²² following Design for All.

WADcher is built with the intention of supporting the different stakeholders when addressing the different legal requirements, while supporting a better and streamlined business process. The Web Accessibility Directive (WAD), its requirements and monitoring procedures, and how WAD compliance can be achieved using WADcher is described in the project's open eBook "WAD and How to be Compliant"²³.

²⁰ <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities.html>

²¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1202>

²² The result of Commission standardisation mandate 473, See: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/standards/topics/accessibility/pages/designforall.aspx>, and <http://www.edf-fepf.org/newsroom/news/first-ever-european-standard-design-all>

²³ WADcher Consortium. (2021, June). "Web Accessibility Directive (WAD) — How to be Compliant" (Version 1.0). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916130>.

4 Project outcomes

The project addresses the challenges people with various degrees of disabilities face when accessing mainstream online products and services, thus being excluded from benefiting from Web content and services on an equal basis as people without disabilities. Marginalising people with disabilities on this level is a critical and problematic issue, especially in today's "Information Society", where access to information should be equally available to all²⁴. While these challenges have been identified (also by the EC with the published Web Accessibility Directive, WAD), they have not yet been addressed efficiently.

Within this context, the **scope of the project is focus on the support of the public sector in the European Union to comply with the requirements of the Web Accessibility Directive (WAD)**. This is described in more detail in this section. The approach of the project was to identify the key stakeholders (section 4.1), which were mapped to a set of services (section 4.2). These services enable a **large-scale hybrid web accessibility assessment** by implementing the monitoring and reporting procedures of the WAD in all European public sector websites, while minimising costs and development time along with increased scalability, accessibility and usability for all stakeholders.

The pyramid showed in Figure 2 represents as a top-bottom approach the total amount of end users and the linked services. The top **Monitoring Service** application is connected to the monitoring bodies. In the center the **Observatory** application is linked to the web commissioners and their projects. On the bottom, the **Decision Support Environment** where Experts and Developers work on Audits (an evaluation instance of a project).

The workflow is top-down. The monitoring bodies create a sample with at least 70 websites. Each of the website owner - the web commissioners - shall create a project. The web commissioners then evaluate a project, and the evaluation result is an audit. Every audit can be released for selected experts and developers. They need to work on audit level which means the experts need to evaluate uncertainties so called "cannot tells" and decide for each uncertainty if it passes or fails. The developer at the end can look in the DSE and see a list of all failures that they must solve. This step is a manual process and requires the input of accessibility experts, especially for the so-called (in WAD terminology) "in-depth" assessment. WADcher supports and optimises this process, but it does not eliminate the need for manual input from the accessibility experts and the web developers.

On the right there is an arrow pointing from the bottom to the top and represents the data aggregation. This means that all these assertions are aggregated to the top level as a sample for the monitoring body. The web commissioner controls the audit and releases it when appropriate to their monitoring service.

²⁴ See state of the art in "Web Accessibility - A Foundation for Research", Editors: Yeliz Yesilada, Middle East Technical University Northern Cyprus Campus, Güzelyurt, Turkey and Simon Harper, School of Computer Science University of Manchester, Manchester, UK, 2019. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-1-4471-7440-0>

Figure 2 Graphical representation of the scope of the project.

4.1 Supported stakeholders

While end users, including people with disabilities, older people and all users, will indirectly benefit from the more accessible web applications that WADcher enables, WADcher primarily provides WAD compliance to the following 4 groups of users that WADcher is directly targeting:

- **WAD Monitoring Bodies and Policy Groups** involved in WAD policy implementation, and eAccessibility generally. These include EU and national WAD Monitoring and Policy bodies. Their endorsement and encouragement of WADcher use are critical to the wide-spread take-up of the service.
- **Web Applications Providers and Commissioners** that mainly include the public sector bodies whose websites that need to comply with the WAD monitoring, reporting and enforcement procedures. But also, private enterprises and organisations responsible for commissioning the content and graphical layout and multimedia content of these websites.
- **Web Developers and Tools Developers/Providers.** The former use WADcher to support them in their development and testing of WAD-compliant accessible web applications. While the latter use the WADcher Open API to integrate their tools into WADcher and its WAD compliance processes.
- **Expert Accessibility Reviewers**, who use the WADcher tools and services, interpret their results, and provide guidance and/or certification of WAD compliance.

4.2 WADcher Services

WADcher outcomes enable public sector bodies, as well as large organisations, SMEs or individuals (developers, designers, accessibility experts, monitoring bodies, policy makers, etc.) to produce websites and mobile applications of superior accessibility and quality, accompanied with appropriate measures, technologies and tools to detect and formally report accessibility hurdles and assisting developers in repairing them.

WADcher provides a holistic and hybrid approach to Web accessibility assessment. The WADcher project has gone beyond state of the art to provide developers, designers, experts and policy makers with an integrated web accessibility and WAD-compliance support

environment. This has been done with a dynamic and personalised environment that enables them, on one hand, to design accessible web applications and, on the other hand, to understand their problems, and analyse and test their accessibility. Within WADcher, the challenge has been to find the way in which technology can be best used to increase accessibility, usability and quality of web applications and services. WADcher integrates both new ICT-driven concepts and user-oriented approaches with methodologies and tools regarding web accessibility assessment. Within this context, and by using lessons learnt from relevant standards, research and best practices (WCAG, EARL,²⁵ etc.).

WADcher is a large-scale infrastructure integrating extended and enhanced existing web accessibility tools making them customizable to the needs of different actors and stakeholders in European Member States, transferable to different sectors in web environments, aiming at minimizing costs and development time while increasing scalability and improving their accessibility and usability to meet the requirements of the WAD. To maximise the effectiveness of a system that is conceived to support, among others, developers and software designers, the environment design has been carefully matched with their workflows and tasks. A User-Centred Design (UCD) has been one of the most important requirements in the WADcher system definition and development.

WADcher enables an organisation to create a “Project” for each of its websites and then periodically run “Audits” to determine their WAD compliance, help generate Accessibility Statements and report to its WAD Monitoring Body.

WADcher comprises the following services:

- **Monitor Service** – mainly for WAD Monitoring Bodies (Figure 5, Figure 6). The Monitor service allows national and regional monitoring bodies to create a distributed sample of public sector bodies, to manage their public sector bodies, create reports for the European Commission and to monitor the accessibility of the websites of public sector bodies in the sample.
- **Observatory** – mainly for Web Commissioners and Managers (Figure 3). The Observatory allows web commissioners to evaluate and manage website evaluations. The results -called audits- can be used in the observatory to create Accessibility Statements, create reports, and visualize results and progress. Additionally, the platform supports the release to the responsible monitoring body (if selected for a sample) and provide access for web accessibility experts and developers.
- **Decision Support Environment (DSE)** – mainly for Accessibility Experts and Developers (Figure 4). The DSE provides an advanced environment to complete manually the accessibility audits, by providing further input on the issues that an automatic tool cannot discern (this is a very well-known restriction of accessibility tools) and are qualified as “cannot tell”. These corrections are then stored by the system and displayed in the Observatory, providing a more accurate view on the results of the audit.
- **WADcher APIs** – for providers of Accessibility Evaluation Tools. See section 4.2.1.

²⁵ Evaluation And Report Language: <https://www.w3.org/TR/EARL10/>

Figure 3. WADcher Observatory displaying an overview of the audit results.

Figure 4. WADcher DSE providing assertions to experts and developers.

Figure 5. WADcher Monitor Service providing to the Monitoring Body a graphical comparison of accessibility audits.

Figure 6. WADcher Monitor Service providing to the Monitoring Body a territorial overview.

The WADcher cloud-based services provide:

- Periodic WAD simplified monitoring and in-depth testing support.
- WAD Evaluation Reports
- Generation of WAD Accessibility Statements
- Evaluation Reports for WAD Monitoring Bodies and Periodic National WAD Compliance Reports, and
- an Open generic API for all Accessibility Tools.

The benefits of WADcher's services are to:

- Support public sector bodies and Member States to monitor, report and enforce WAD-compliance on a large scale.
- Improve the lack of knowledge/skills for building accessible web and mobile applications with monitoring and evaluation tools.
- Provide a harmonized set of procedures based on semantic standards (EARL) to avoid different interpretations of accessibility evaluations.
- Reduce accessibility and WAD compliance implementation costs.
- Support the integration of different accessibility assessment tools to improve the depth and reliability of accessibility testing results.

WADcher's specific benefits for its targeted users are shown in the following table:

WADcher Benefits for each User Group	WAD Compliance Evaluation	WAD Periodic Simplified Monitoring	WAD Periodic In-Depth Testing.	WAD Accessibility Statements	Evaluation Reports for WAD Monitoring Bodies	Periodic National WAD Compliance Reports.	WADcher Open generic API for all Accessibility Tools
WAD Monitoring and Policy Bodies	X	X			X	X	X

WADcher Benefits for each User Group	WAD Compliance Evaluation	WAD Periodic Simplified Monitoring	WAD Periodic In-Depth Testing.	WAD Accessibility Statements	Evaluation Reports for WAD Monitoring Bodies	Periodic National WAD Compliance Reports.	WADcher Open generic API for all Accessibility Tools
Web Applications Commissioners and Providers	X	X	X	X	X		
Web Content Developers and Tools Providers	X	X	X				X
Expert Accessibility Reviewers	X		X				

Table 1 WADcher benefits for each user group.

4.2.1 WADcher APIs

The WADcher Public APIs are defined and freely available at the [WADcher APIs Home Page](#). The WADcher APIs are an open set of HTTP REST and asynchronous messaging interfaces (including models and interfaces) that enable any Accessibility Evaluation Tool to use the WADcher platform.

The WADcher APIs are Accessibility Tool agnostic by using a common semantic vocabulary required for accessibility standards/recommendations, consisting of selected: Evaluation and Report Language (EARL²⁶) with **Assertions** addressing:

- **Assertor** - who or what ran the test
- **Test Subject** - what is being tested: web content (web pages, videos, applets, etc.), software, etc.
- **Test Criterion** - what are we evaluating the test subject against: a specification, a set of guidelines, etc.
- **Test Result** - what was the outcome of the test

The WADcher APIs consist of the following APIs:

1. **Rulesets API**. This API is used by the WADcher platform to communicate with an external web accessibility testing tool to find out which ruleset or set of rulesets are supported by the tool.
2. **Assertion API**. This API is used by the WADcher platform to insert/update assertions in the results of an audit performed by a web accessibility testing tool.
3. **Assertions API**. This API is used by the WADcher platform to communicate with an external web accessibility testing tool to stream the assertions of an audit result.
4. **Audit API**. This API is used by the WADcher platform to communicate with an external web accessibility testing tool to start an audit.
5. **AuditResults API**. This API is used by the WADcher platform to communicate with an external web accessibility testing tool to stream the results of an audit.

²⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/EARL10-Schema>

6. **Test Subject (source) API.** This API is used by the WADcher platform (in particular, the DSE) to extract the HTML rendered source code out of a tested resource (test subject) in an audit.

WADcher Public APIs Home Page

This site contains the [WADcher Public APIs](#), described with the [OpenAPI 3.0.3 specification](#). These APIs are used by WADcher to communicate with external web accessibility testing tools, or for the communication within internal components of the platform.

- Overview page: <https://api.wadcher.fit.fraunhofer.de/api/v1/>
- API release version: **0.7.9**

Below you find direct links to different API subsections.

Rulesets API

Documentation of the **WADcher rulesets API**. This API is used by the WADcher platform to communicate with an external web accessibility testing tool to find out which ruleset or set of rulesets are supported by the tool.

[Visit the rulesets API](#)

Assertion API

Documentation of the **WADcher assertion API**. This API is used by the WADcher platform to insert/update assertions in the results of an audit performed by a web accessibility testing tool.

[Visit the assertion API](#)

Figure 7 WADcher APIs Homepage.

4.3 Automatic Evaluation Tools

Automatic web accessibility assessment is the core procedure of WADcher's automatic assessment framework and is conducted by several external tools connected to the WADcher platform. There are now 4 available tools connected: imergo[®], MAUVE, WaaT and Madis. In the context of WADcher a common interface is provided independent of the tool working in the background which allows the easy integration of new tools.

4.3.1 imergo[®] Web Compliance Suite

The imergo[®] Web Compliance Suite²⁷ is a complete software suite targeted to improve the quality of web applications by providing a flexible testing framework that can address a wide variety of requirements off-the-shelf, such as mark-up validation and web accessibility. Additionally, it supports the extension of its rule sets through a complete API that allows complex testing of different types of web applications.

The imergo[®] Web Compliance Suite checks for compliance with international accessibility requirements (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 2.1). imergo[®] contains a crawling service that downloads a set of web pages through a flexible configuration. imergo[®] evaluates dynamic web pages through its powerful rendering engine, including JavaScript and stylesheets, and can be configured to act as a mobile browser to detect accessibility issues in the mobile web.

²⁷ <https://imergo.com/>

4.3.2 MAUVE

MAUVE²⁸ is a validator tool able to validate guidelines specified through an XML-based language, and externally stored, in order to facilitate its updating to support validation of new guidelines. Before the start of the project, it supported validation of WCAG 2.0, Stanca Law, and vision-impaired guidelines. It can validate various device-specific versions of a website (Desktop, Tablet, Smartphone, ...), and dynamic websites validation through browsers' plugins. It also provides Web developers-oriented report system, with indications of the accessibility problems directly into web page source code. For integration in WADcher it is being extended to support validation of WCAG 2.1, the Evaluation and Report Language (EARL) W3C format for expressing test results, and the WADcher API for communication with the other tools developed in the project.

4.3.3 WaaT

WaaT²⁹ is a web applications assessment tool, developed in the context of ACCESSIBLE³⁰ project, for the accessibility evaluation of web applications by enabling the personalized accessibility assessment according to WCAG 2.0 as well as WAI-ARIA guidelines using virtual user models. WaaT supports also markup validation for the assessment of the conformance of a webpage against the technical specifications of HTML and XHTML. It produces an EARL report in XML format as well as a PDF version of the EARL based report. WaaT has been extended for the integration with WADcher by supporting WCAG 2.1 and the defined API specification of WADcher's tools.

4.3.4 Madis

One of the biggest challenges of WADcher project has been the development of an open and extensible architecture which will allow the seamless integration of third-party accessibility evaluation tools. In the consortium, there were three web accessibility tools which have been used to develop a suitable architecture. However, aiming at evaluating the effectiveness of the architecture, external tools needed to be tested. A first evaluation of the architecture has been achieved through the integration of a popular open-source evaluation tool, QualWeb.³¹

As a first step, a reference implementation of a hypothetical WADCher-enabled evaluation tool was developed. This is a minimal implementation of the open APIs and formats plus a mechanism for producing random but still valid (according the WADcher specifications) results. The tool has been used internally to allow extensibility and/or easy integration with existing tools. Furthermore, this tool has been widely used by the consortium for running integration tests.

The next step was to evaluate the WADCher integration process through the integration of a third-party tool. QualWeb is a tool developed using NodeJS³²/Typescript technologies and based on Puppeteer,³³ a Node library which provides a high-level API to control Chrome or

²⁸ <https://mauve.isti.cnr.it/>

²⁹ <https://sourceforge.net/projects/waat/>

³⁰ <http://www.accessible-eu.org/index.html>

³¹ <https://github.com/qualweb>

³² <https://nodejs.org/>

³³ <https://pptr.dev/>

Chromium over the DevTools Protocol³⁴ under headless mode. For the implementation, the reference implementation has been used and QualWeb has been used as a “black box”, i.e., working only at its input and output. The most challenging task for such an integration was the integration of different formats and especially the reporting formats. Even if QualWeb supports EARL, as any semantic language, there are different ways to serialise the data. The approach selected by the project was to always use the JSON-LD³⁵ serialisation in its canonical form.

³⁴ <https://chromedevtools.github.io/devtools-protocol/>

³⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/>

5 WADcher Pilot Reference Sites

As with all innovative software solutions, a structured evaluation and testing process was implemented to fully understand the workings and potential issues that might arise through the implementation of new accessibility evaluation and improvement methods. The WADcher system was pilot trialed in 2 phases at 20 pilot sites in Austria, Greece, Italy and Ireland during the project, with the following overall objectives:

- WADcher tools evaluation and validation
- Periodic WAD simplified monitoring and in-depth testing
- WAD Evaluation Reports
- Generating WAD Accessibility Statements
- Periodic National WAD Reports

The Pilot Testing during the project used a two phased approach where the first phase consisted of general quality checks through the partner organisations themselves and on the websites of these organisations. This was conducted mainly to ensure, that the pilot application was running smoothly and could deliver evaluation results and recommendations, according to the best knowledge available and in line with the WAD procedures. The success of the pilot actions as well as the whole setup of the first pilot phase set the baseline for starting the second pilot phase and evaluating whether the revised monitoring environment more closely matches the requirements put forward by the web commissioners, expert reviewers, web developers and monitoring bodies.

The second phase of Pilot trials provided extensive detailed testing and validation of the complete WADcher system and all its services with its targeted users across 4 Member States of the EU. This second testing phase provided improvements for the WADcher services and its post project productization. They also confirm that WADcher's open public API successfully enables third-party accessibility evaluation tools to integrate into the complete WAD compliance functionality of the WADcher system.

6 Future steps

WADcher is now available as a validated cloud-based Software as a Service (SaaS) prototype integrated system, that greatly reduces the costs of web apps WAD compliance adherence, including designing and testing, assessing and on-going monitoring and maintenance. Now that the major WADcher service components have been prototyped and validated, the plan is to begin a 6 to 12 month “productisation” of WADcher into a sustainable commercial WAD compliance service in collaboration with existing tools providers. The partners will earn fees for their web assessment tools and major WADcher components (Observatory, DSE and Monitor Services). The WADcher API to external assessment tools is free and open source, to encourage takeup.

With a clear IPR distribution of ownership, the Consortium is looking for additional partnerships/investors and sponsorships that guarantee the sustainability of the infrastructure and the necessary personnel resources with a long-term plan.

7 Contact and acknowledgements

WADcher (Web Accessibility Directive Decision Support Environment) received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780206. <https://wadcher.eu/>

Contact:

- Dr. Yehya Mohamad and Dr. Carlos A. Velasco
Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology FIT
- E-mail: webcc@fit.fraunhofer.de